

Actors' Engagement in the Perspective of Value Co-Creation: A Case Study of the Tour Guide Mobile Application

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ABSTRACT: This study focuses on identifying the key value drivers that foster actor engagement within *Guidemu*, a mobile-based tour guide service platform in Indonesia. Actor engagement plays a vital role in enabling collaborative value creation, particularly in digitally mediated tourism services. Adopting a qualitative approach rooted in a constructivist paradigm, this research engaged nine participants such as platform managers, tour guides, and tourists, through semi-structured interviews to explore their motivations, expectations, and perceived benefits of using the application. Thematic analysis revealed five dominant categories of value drivers: economic, experiential, functional, social, and strategic. Economic value relates to income opportunities and operational efficiency; experiential value emphasizes enjoyment and self-development through local experiences; functional value highlights ease of use, platform reliability, and service accessibility; social value includes recognition, trust-building, and meaningful interactions within the tourism community; while strategic value refers to personal branding and long-term career alignment. These value drivers shape actor perceptions and determine the quality and intensity of their engagement with the platform. The findings suggest that a deeper understanding of these drivers is essential for improving platform design, enhancing service satisfaction, and encouraging sustainable participation from diverse tourism stakeholders. By highlighting the motivational underpinnings of actor engagement, this article contributes to the literature on value co-creation in tourism technology and offers practical insights for application developers, tourism managers, and policymakers who aim to support more inclusive and resilient digital service ecosystems.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The rapid digital transformation of the tourism industry has led to the emergence of mobile applications as essential tools in enhancing tourist experiences, streamlining service delivery, and enabling more participatory service ecosystems (Neuhof et al., 2015). Among these applications, mobile-based tour guide services represent a new wave of tourism innovation that integrates technology with localized knowledge and human interaction. One such application is *Guidemu*, a startup platform in Indonesia that connects tourists with local tour guides through a user-friendly mobile interface. In such platforms, the engagement of various actors is fundamental to value creation. Their continuous involvement ensures that the platform evolves in response to user needs and environmental demands (Pralhad & Ramaswamy, 2004). *Guidemu* operates in a developing country context where digital literacy, local tourism practices, and economic conditions influence platform usage. Unlike global platforms such as Airbnb Experiences or GetYourGuide, which may benefit from strong branding and global reach, local platforms like *Guidemu* must build trust and demonstrate immediate value to retain users. This situation makes the study of value drivers in *Guidemu* particularly relevant, as it offers insights into localized engagement strategies that are sensitive to context and culture.

The concept of actor engagement in digital service ecosystems is closely tied to the theoretical underpinnings of Service-

Dominant Logic (Vargo & Lusch, 2008) and value co-creation (Ranjan & Read, 2016). In this paradigm, value is no longer produced unilaterally by firms but co-created interactively through the integration of resources, competencies, and relationships among various stakeholders. Actor engagement thus becomes a critical micro-foundation of value co-creation, particularly in the tourism sector where intangible elements like trust, authenticity, and personal experience are central to service delivery (Chathoth et al., 2013).

This research focuses on one core question: “What are the key value drivers that foster actor engagement in *Guidemu*?” Understanding this question is crucial, not only for theoretical development but also for practical implementation, as engagement mechanisms determine the success or failure of many digital tourism platforms. The concept of “value drivers” refers to factors that motivate and sustain the participation of users in a platform or service. These may include both extrinsic and intrinsic rewards, perceived benefits, emotional connections, and alignment with personal or professional goals (Brodie et al., 2011).

In the broader context of tourism, digital platforms are reshaping how services are accessed, experienced, and evaluated. Mobile applications enable real-time interaction, personalized offerings, and peer-to-peer exchanges that transform traditional provider-customer dynamics (Buhalis & Amaranggana, 2015). However, the effectiveness of such platforms depends heavily on actor engagement. Low engagement levels often result in inactive communities, poor service feedback, and stagnated platform growth. Therefore, identifying what drives engagement is vital to sustaining a vibrant and functional service ecosystem, especially from the actor’s perspective.

Research in tourism and service marketing has established several dimensions of actor engagement, including cognitive, emotional, and behavioral aspects (Hollebeek et al., 2014). In mobile tourism applications, cognitive engagement relates to users’ understanding and mental involvement with the app features; emotional engagement reflects satisfaction, enjoyment, and a sense of belonging; while behavioral engagement is evidenced through frequency of use, feedback provision, and advocacy. Each of these dimensions is influenced by different value drivers that may vary according to user type, cultural background, and situational context (So et al., 2016).

Existing literature suggests that value drivers in tourism platforms can be grouped into several categories. Economic value includes tangible benefits like income generation, cost-efficiency, and transaction transparency (Tussyadiah & Pesonen, 2016). Experiential value encompasses enjoyment, novelty, learning opportunities, and meaningful interactions. Functional value relates to ease of use, technological reliability, and service accessibility (Gretzel et al., 2015). Social value includes community recognition, status enhancement, and network expansion. Finally, strategic value involves long-term professional development, personal branding, and alignment with career goals (Sigala, 2016).

In the Indonesian tourism context, studies have shown that local tour guides often seek platforms that not only offer monetary compensation but also provide visibility, professional growth, and connections with travelers who share mutual interests (Utami & Darma, 2020). Tourists, on the other hand, value authentic, personalized, and socially meaningful travel experiences that differ from standard package tours. These expectations form the basis for engagement and must be understood as part of a dynamic co-creation process (Komppula, 2014).

Moreover, the digital infrastructure and service orientation of the *Guidemu* platform play a mediating role in how these value drivers are perceived and acted upon. An intuitive interface, efficient matching algorithm, and feedback system can enhance functional and strategic value, while storytelling features and local cultural integration may boost experiential and social value. As such, actor engagement is not only a psychological or behavioral outcome but also a design concern embedded in the technology itself (Yoo et al., 2010). By narrowing the scope of analysis to actor engagement in *Guidemu* and focusing on the value drivers that sustain it, this study provides a grounded understanding of how engagement mechanisms operate in emerging digital tourism ecosystems. The research not only advances theoretical discussions in service-dominant logic and actor-network theory but also generates actionable insights for digital tourism entrepreneurs and platform developers seeking to build more inclusive, adaptive, and sustainable services.

Ultimately, the significance of this study lies in its capacity to bridge theory and practice. While existing frameworks offer abstract models of co-creation and engagement, this study contextualizes those ideas in a real-world digital tourism platform. It brings forth the voices and experiences of actual actors (platform managers, guides, and tourists) whose motivations shape the evolution of tourism technology. In doing so, it contributes to a deeper, more relational understanding of value in tourism, not as a product to be delivered but as a lived experience to be shared and co-created.

2. METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a qualitative research design grounded in a constructivist paradigm to explore the key value drivers that foster actor engagement in the *Guidemu* mobile tour guide platform. The constructivist approach is appropriate given the study’s aim to understand the subjective meanings, expectations, and motivations of diverse actors involved in the service ecosystem (Lincoln & Guba, 1985; Creswell & Poth, 2018). A single case study strategy was employed to provide an in-depth contextual analysis of the *Guidemu* platform as a bounded system of actor interaction and engagement (Yin, 2018). Participants in this study consisted of nine individuals: two *Guidemu* platform managers, four tour guides registered as service providers, and three tourists who had used the

application. Table 1 presents the demographic and engagement profiles of the participants involved in this study.

Table 1: Participant Profile

Code	Role	Gender	Age	Duration with Guidemu	Interview Format
M1	Platform Manager	M	35	>2 years	In-person
M2	Platform Manager	F	33	>2 years	In-person
G1	Tour Guide	F	29	1.5 years	In-person
G2	Tour Guide	M	41	1 year	In-person
G3	Tour Guide	M	38	1 year	In-person
G4	Tour Guide	F	30	2 years	In-person
T1	Tourist	M	32	3 months	In-person
T2	Tourist	F	27	5 months	In-person
T3	Tourist	F	40	6 months	In-person

Purposive sampling was used to ensure that participants had direct experience with the platform and could reflect meaningfully on their engagement motivations (Patton, 2015). The diversity of actor roles allowed for the triangulation of perspectives and a richer understanding of value drivers across different stakeholder groups. Data were collected through semi-structured in-depth interviews, each lasting approximately 45 to 60 minutes. Interviews were conducted face-to-face and via video calls, depending on participant availability and geographical location. All interviews were recorded with participant consent and transcribed verbatim for analysis. The semi-structured format enabled consistency in questioning while allowing for flexible probing to capture rich narratives and personal experiences (DiCicco-Bloom & Crabtree, 2006). The interview questions were guided by themes derived from the literature on actor engagement and value co-creation in service ecosystems. Core questions included: (1) Can you describe your experience using or participating in the *Guidemu* application? (2) What motivates you to use or continue using the *Guidemu* platform? (3) What do you personally value or expect from your engagement with this application? (4) Have you experienced any benefits, either economic or non-economic, from your involvement? (5) What aspects of the platform do you find most useful or important?

Thematic analysis was used to code and interpret the interview transcripts (Braun & Clarke, 2006). An inductive approach guided the identification of emerging value categories and motivational themes, allowing insights to be grounded in the lived experiences of participants. Coding was conducted in three stages: open coding to identify initial concepts, axial coding to explore relationships among codes, and selective coding to refine themes related to actor engagement and value drivers (Strauss & Corbin, 1998). To ensure trustworthiness, the study implemented triangulation by comparing perspectives across different actor roles (Flick, 2018). Member checking was conducted by sharing preliminary findings with participants for validation. An audit trail was maintained to document the analytical process and decision-making. Ethical clearance was obtained from the institutional research board, and informed consent was collected from all participants prior to data collection. This methodology enabled a rich, contextualized understanding of the factors that encourage sustained engagement in a digital tourism platform, contributing new insights to the field of tourism service co-creation and digital actor participation.

3. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

This study identified five key value drivers that shape actor engagement in the *Guidemu* mobile tour guide platform: economic, experiential, functional, social, and strategic value. These findings were generated from thematic analysis of qualitative data and are discussed here in conjunction with relevant literature to enrich theoretical insight and contextual understanding (see Table 2).

Table 2: Categories of Value Drivers and Representative Narratives

Value Category	Core Description	Example Quote
Economic	Financial benefits and efficient transactions	“I no longer need to split commission with an agency. Everything goes directly to me.”
Experiential	Personal satisfaction and cultural sharing	“I enjoy when tourists ask about our traditions, it feels meaningful.”
Functional	Ease of use and platform reliability	“The automated schedule makes my work more organized.”
Social	Recognition and trust from the community	“Getting positive reviews motivates me to give better service.”
Strategic	Career development and personal branding	“I want to be known as a professional guide in Indonesia.”

Economic Value

Economic value emerged as a primary driver for engagement, particularly among tour guides and platform managers. Guides reported that using *Guidemu* enabled them to generate direct income by attracting tourists independently, thus bypassing traditional

agency intermediaries. This aligns with the concept of economic value as defined by Tussyadiah and Pesonen (2016), who found that perceived financial gain enhances user participation in digital tourism platforms. In the case of *Guidemu*, actors viewed the platform as a cost-effective tool for self-promotion and client acquisition, suggesting that transparency and autonomy in financial transactions increase trust and sustained involvement.

Experiential Value

Experiential value was another significant motivator for both tourists and tour guides. Tourists described their experiences with *Guidemu* as more personal, flexible, and culturally immersive compared to traditional guided tours. Likewise, guides expressed satisfaction from sharing their heritage, meeting diverse travelers, and engaging in meaningful conversations. These narratives resonate with the findings of Komppula (2014), who emphasized that co-created tourism experiences yield emotional rewards that deepen engagement. Neuhofer et al. (2015) also argue that digitally mediated experiences enhance tourists' sense of personalization and interaction, reinforcing the importance of emotional connection in co-creative service contexts.

Functional Value

Functional value was consistently cited across all participant groups. The application's user-friendly interface, real-time communication features, and clear booking system were seen as critical to effective engagement. Tourists praised the app's search filters and map integration, while guides found scheduling tools and messaging notifications especially useful. These findings support previous studies by Gretzel et al. (2015), who highlighted ease of use and technological reliability as essential enablers of digital service adoption. Hollebeek et al. (2014) note that cognitive engagement forms the basis for deeper emotional and behavioral involvement, driven by clarity and platform efficiency.

Social Value

Social value was identified in terms of trust, community recognition, and interpersonal relationships. Guides particularly valued positive reviews and ratings, which enhanced their credibility and encouraged more bookings. Tourists enjoyed the feeling of being part of a localized travel community, describing their interactions with guides as "friendly," "authentic," and "enriching." These accounts align with the notion of social capital in digital services, where reputation, trustworthiness, and peer validation drive user loyalty (Sigala, 2016). Brodie et al. (2011) also argue that engagement is inherently relational and strengthened by mutual recognition and emotional reciprocity within service ecosystems.

Strategic Value

Strategic value was especially relevant for tour guides who viewed *Guidemu* not only as a source of income but as a professional development tool. Several guides described the platform as a way to build personal branding, enhance digital marketing skills, and align with long-term career goals in the tourism industry. This reflects the insights of Ranjan and Read (2016), who conceptualize value co-creation as a strategic process of capability building and self-extension. By integrating their knowledge, skills, and aspirations with the app, guides became co-designers of the service experience, which in turn reinforced their sense of ownership and commitment.

Discussion

The interplay of these five value drivers reveals that actor engagement in digital tourism platforms is multi-dimensional and context-sensitive. While economic and functional values may prompt initial engagement, experiential, social, and strategic values appear critical for sustaining long-term involvement. The *Guidemu* platform serves as a mediating structure that facilitates not only service transactions but also emotional, relational, and professional outcomes for its users.

The findings also underscore the importance of actor-centric design in tourism platforms. As Vargo and Lusch (2008) suggest in their Service-Dominant Logic, value is co-created through interactions among actors who integrate resources within institutional and technological arrangements. *Guidemu*'s success in fostering engagement stems from its ability to accommodate diverse value perceptions and create avenues for their realization. For instance, a simple feedback feature contributes to social value, while platform analytics support strategic decision-making by managers and guides.

In comparison with global platforms such as Airbnb Experiences or Viator, *Guidemu* reflects a hyperlocal model that emphasizes cultural proximity and grassroots participation. This localization increases relevance and resonance, particularly in a country like Indonesia where tourism narratives are highly contextual. According to Utami and Darma (2020), digital entrepreneurship in the tourism sector must align with local identity and stakeholder dynamics to gain legitimacy and traction. The findings of this study affirm that value co-creation is not only an outcome of design features but also of contextual responsiveness and actor inclusivity.

Theoretically, this study contributes to a refined understanding of actor engagement by grounding value drivers in lived experiences rather than prescriptive models. It adds empirical nuance to frameworks proposed by scholars such as Hollebeek et al. (2014) and Brodie et al. (2011), showing how different types of value intersect and reinforce each other in a tourism-specific context. Practically, the insights are valuable for developers of digital tourism applications. Features that support self-expression, peer feedback, and micro-entrepreneurship can enhance strategic and social value, while intuitive interfaces and secure transactions

ensure functional and economic engagement. Policymakers and tourism boards may also use these findings to promote inclusive platform ecosystems that empower local actors and preserve cultural integrity. In sum, actor engagement in Guidemu is not driven by a single value proposition but by an evolving mix of instrumental and affective factors. Recognizing and designing for this complexity is essential for building resilient and co-creative digital tourism ecosystems that benefit all stakeholders.

4. CONCLUSION

This study explored the value drivers that foster actor engagement within the *Guidemu* mobile tour guide platform in Indonesia, drawing from qualitative insights provided by platform managers, tour guides, and tourists. Through thematic analysis, five key value categories emerged—economic, experiential, functional, social, and strategic—which together constitute a comprehensive framework for understanding engagement in digital tourism service ecosystems. These findings reinforce theoretical perspectives from Service-Dominant Logic and value co-creation literature, affirming that actor engagement is not a unidimensional construct but a dynamic interplay of motivational, emotional, and strategic factors.

The study shows that economic and functional values are essential for initial adoption, while experiential, social, and strategic values are crucial for sustained participation. This multi-layered understanding provides both scholarly contributions and practical implications. For researchers, it offers a grounded model that contextualizes actor engagement within localized digital platforms. For developers and tourism practitioners, the findings suggest that platform features should support not only usability and transaction efficiency but also social recognition, storytelling, and capacity building to enhance stakeholder satisfaction and retention.

Despite its contributions, this study has several limitations. First, its single case study design limits the generalizability of findings beyond the *Guidemu* context. Actor motivations may differ across regions, cultures, or types of digital tourism services. Second, the study focused on retrospective self-reports, which may be subject to recall bias. Third, the exclusion of tourists with minimal app usage might have overlooked perspectives from disengaged users.

Future research could explore longitudinal engagement patterns over time or apply comparative analysis across multiple platforms in different cultural settings. Quantitative studies may also be valuable to validate the proposed value categories and assess their predictive power on engagement behaviors. Additionally, future work could examine platform design elements more deeply to understand how technological affordances shape engagement dynamics in real-time. Ultimately, as digital tourism platforms evolve, understanding the nuanced and context-specific drivers of actor engagement will remain critical to sustaining innovation, participation, and shared value in tourism ecosystems.

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